

Preliminary Life Cycle Assessment of a High-Performance Computing Data Center: A Case Study of the HPC4AI Facility at the University of Turin

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Abstract—High-performance computing (HPC) and artificial intelligence (AI) data centers are increasingly recognized as critical infrastructures for scientific research, yet they are also associated with significant environmental burdens due to their high energy intensity and rapid technological obsolescence. Traditional performance metrics such as Power Usage Effectiveness (PUE) primarily capture operational efficiency and fail to account for embodied impacts related to construction, equipment manufacturing, and component replacement. This study presents a preliminary Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) of the HPC4AI data center at the University of Turin, conducted in accordance with ISO 14040–44 [1] and structured using the EN 15978 modular framework. The assessment adopts a screening-level, attributional LCA with a 30-year reference study period, integrating primary inventory data derived from seven detailed design and equipment schedules covering architectural elements, IT infrastructure, electrical systems, lighting, and cooling equipment. Life-cycle impacts are quantified for the modules A1–A3 (product stage), B4 (replacement due to technological obsolescence), and B6 (operational energy use), while other modules are structurally included as placeholders. Global warming potential (GWP) is used as the impact indicator, with multiple electricity mix scenarios applied to evaluate operational sensitivity. Results indicate that operational electricity use (Module B6) is the dominant contributor to life-cycle GWP, confirming findings from recent HPC and AI data center LCAs. However, embodied impacts associated with IT and cooling equipment manufacturing and replacement (A1–A3 + B4) represent a substantial secondary contribution, with replacement impacts of comparable magnitude to initial construction. A component-level ranking reveals that servers, UPS systems, and core cooling equipment are the principal sources of embodied emissions, while architectural components contribute marginally. The study highlights the critical role of electricity decarbonization, hardware lifetime management, and circular strategies in reducing the environmental footprint of academic HPC facilities. Despite its screening nature, the LCA provides a robust baseline for future refined assessments and supports the integration of life-cycle thinking into the design and governance of research-oriented data centers.

Keywords—Life Cycle Assessment (LCA), data centers, Global Warming Potential (GWP), Embodied and operational emissions

I. INTRODUCTION

The exponential growth of global digitalization has resulted in an unprecedented expansion of data center infrastructure, which forms the backbone of cloud computing, artificial intelligence (AI), and high-performance computing (HPC) ecosystems. As of 2024, data centers are estimated to consume 1–2 % of global electricity and contribute roughly 0.3–0.5 % of global CO₂ emissions [3] their rapid proliferation raises concerns about both operational energy use and embodied impacts associated with the manufacture, maintenance, and end-of-life phases of ICT hardware and supporting infrastructure.

Usually, energy efficiency metrics such as Power Usage Effectiveness (PUE) and Data Center Infrastructure Efficiency (DCiE) have been used to benchmark environmental performance. However, these single-issue indicators consider only operational energy consumption and overlook upstream and downstream impacts. In contrast, Life Cycle Assessment (LCA), standardized under ISO 14040/44 [1,2], provides a multi-criteria, cradle-to-grave framework encompassing manufacturing, transport, use, and end-of-life stages [3,4].

LCA computes multiple environmental indicators such as climate change, abiotic resource depletion, acidification, particulate matter formation, and human toxicity, allowing for holistic comparisons between design alternatives and technologies.

Recent studies confirm that the environmental burden of data centers extends far beyond operational energy. For example, in a UK Tier III facility, electricity generation dominated total impacts, however the embodied effects of IT hardware and metal refining waste were comparable to mechanical and electrical operational impacts [5]. Similarly, a Tier IV facility in Turkey showed that 98 % of total impacts stemmed from electricity consumption, with the remainder attributable to material inputs and end-of-life processes [6]. These findings reinforce the necessity of integrating embodied and operational aspects within a single methodological framework.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

A. Evolution of Data Center LCA Research

First, early applications of LCA to data centers were limited to cooling systems, such as the Green Room concept developed by Teliasonera [7]. This study applied SimaPro v7.2 with the ReCiPe impact method and found that the utilization phase dominated impacts in all categories except ozone depletion, where the refrigerant R134a was the main contributor. Later, Whitehead et al. (2015) extended the system boundary to the full building, introducing a hybrid LCA approach that combined process-based and economic input–output data to overcome data scarcity. Their model, encompassing mechanical, electrical, IT, and structural subsystems, established a screening benchmark for Tier III UK data centers and identified three sensitivity drivers [5]:

- 1) operational energy for IT and cooling;
- 2) national energy mix;
- 3) the quantity and refresh rate of IT equipment.

Subsequent regional case studies expanded the geographical scope. The first Tier IV LCA of a data center in Turkey was conducted using the CML 2001 method [6]. The results confirmed that electricity consumption accounted for 98.4% of total environmental impacts, with cooling responsible for approximately 30% of energy use. When compared with U.S. averages [10], Turkish data centers exhibited 10–20 % higher carbon footprints due to the fossil-intensive electricity mix [6].

Solar-powered edge data centers were evaluated against conventional designs, introducing refurbished servers and hybrid energy mixes [4]. Using the NegaOctet database [8] and multicriteria indicators (climate change, abiotic depletion, acidification, ionizing radiation), the study reported impact reductions of 11–60 % across categories, rising to 92 % when powered predominantly by solar energy [4].

B. Scope, Functional Units, and Phases Considered

Across studies, LCA boundaries generally follow the four official phases: manufacturing, distribution, use, and end-of-life [4,6]. Functional units vary according to the study objective, per kWh of IT service (energy-based) or per kW of IT capacity (time-based), to define equivalence between systems. For example, one study defined the functional unit as 1 kW of IT capacity per year [5], while another considered IT hosting for five servers and one router over a 15-year period [4]. Despite methodological differences, most studies agree that the manufacturing and use phases dominate environmental impacts, particularly due to semiconductor fabrication and electricity consumption [6].

In AI-intensive and high-performance computing (HPC) environments, the use phase is particularly sensitive to electricity mix and server utilization rate. A recent assessment showed that relocating AI data center operations from Germany to France could reduce lifecycle carbon emissions by 76% due to France’s nuclear-dominated grid, while extending server lifespans from 5 to 7 years lowered emissions by up to 19% [3].

C. Methodological approach

Most data center LCAs employ process-based modelling supported by databases such as Ecoinvent, NegaOctet, or GaBi. Tools including SimaPro and CCaLC are standard, and impact methods typically follow ReCiPe, CML 2001, or Eco-

Indicator 99 conventions. Advanced studies integrate attributional and consequential LCA perspectives to consider both direct and systemic effects [4]. Hybrid approaches, merging process data with economic input–output tables, help address data gaps in proprietary hardware and cooling infrastructure. A growing number of evaluations also consider AI workloads. The 2024 Carbon Footprint of AI Data Centers study incorporated both Product Carbon Footprint (PCF) and Product Environmental Profile (PEP) data to model entire architectures, finding that the use phase contributed 29% and manufacturing 70% of total emissions [3]. The authors recommended expanding analyses beyond CO₂ to include toxicity and resource indicators.

D. Barriers and Challenges

Despite progress, significant barriers limit comprehensive LCAs of data centers:

- *Data confidentiality and granularity*: Many operators withhold bill-of-materials or component-level inventories, limiting transparency [3].
- *Rapid technological obsolescence*: Frequent hardware refresh cycles complicate consistent temporal boundaries and comparability [12].
- *Geographical heterogeneity*: Electricity carbon intensity and cooling requirements vary by region, leading to inconsistent results across studies [6].
- *Limited coverage of non-CO₂ indicators*: Few analyses include water use, toxicity, or circularity metrics despite their growing relevance [4].
- *Dynamic load management*: The non-linear scaling of workloads and cooling efficiencies is difficult to model with static assumptions [4].

E. Key Findings and Comparative Results

Reference [4] provides the basis for **Table I**, which summarizes phase contributions: manufacturing + use phases ≈ 90–95 % of total impacts, with *servers* and *building structure* as dominant contributors. Comparative LCAs across designs yield consistent insights.

TABLE I. SUMMARY OF FINDINGS IN THE LITERATURE REVIEW.

Study	System / Region	Method	Dominant Phases	Impact Reduction Strategies
Oliveira (2012) [7]	Cooling system, Sweden	ISO 14040 + ReCiPe	Use phase	Free cooling, refrigerant substitution
Whitehead et al. (2015) [5]	Tier III UK DC	Hybrid LCA	Use > Embodied	Monitor IT refresh / energy mix
Üçtuğ & Ünver (2023) [6]	Tier IV Turkey	CML 2001 / Ecoinvent	Use (98 %)	Cooling + UPS optimization
Samaye et al. (2025) [4]	Edge DC France	ISO 14040 / NegaOctet	Manufacturing + Use	Solar power + server refurbishment
d’Orgeval et al. (2024) [3]	AI DC Europe	PCF/PEP Hybrid	Manufacturing (70 %)	Clean grid + longer lifespans
Bux et al. (2024) [12]	Theoretical 1 DC Italy	LCA CO _{2e} Calculator	Use (60–70 %)	Efficient infrastructure + natural gas backup

F. Conclusions and Future Directions

The reviewed literature consistently indicates that electricity mix, server lifespan, and cooling efficiency represent the most influential levers for improving the environmental sustainability of data centers. Previous studies show that integrating low-carbon electricity sources and circular hardware strategies, such as server lifetime extension and refurbishment, can reduce life-cycle impacts by 30–90%, depending on geographical context and system configuration [4].

Despite these advances, current research remains largely carbon-centric and often relies on simplified representations of data center operation. There is a growing need to expand data center LCAs beyond global warming potential to include additional environmental dimensions, such as water depletion, human toxicity, resource scarcity, and circularity-related indicators [4]. Moreover, the increasing complexity and variability of AI- and HPC-driven workloads challenge static assumptions and call for more adaptive assessment frameworks.

In this perspective, digital twins and AI-driven monitoring systems are increasingly recognized as enabling technologies for dynamic life cycle assessments capable of reflecting time-dependent operational conditions. The integration of environmental LCA with economic (LCC) and social (S-LCA) assessments is also essential to support holistic sustainability evaluations of digital infrastructure systems.

Within this context, the present study provides a preliminary, screening-level Life Cycle Assessment of the HPC4AI data center infrastructure in Turin [13]. Rather than delivering a dynamic or real-time representation of data center operations, the study establishes a static, EN 15978-aligned baseline that captures the relative importance of operational and embodied impacts over the life cycle. This baseline supports transparent hotspot identification and comparability with existing LCA studies on HPC and AI-oriented data centers, while laying the groundwork for future extensions based on dynamic operational data enabled by BIM-based digital twins.

III. METHODOLOGY

A. Life Cycle Assessment framework

The environmental assessment of the HPC4AI data center at the University of Turin was conducted using the Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) methodology, in accordance with ISO 14040 [1] and ISO 14044 [2] and structured following the EN 15978 modular framework for building-related environmental assessments. This framework was selected to ensure a transparent and consistent life-cycle representation of a complex, equipment-intensive infrastructure such as an HPC data center.

LCA enables a comprehensive, multi-criteria evaluation of environmental impacts across the entire life cycle of a data center, capturing not only operational energy use but also embodied impacts associated with construction, equipment manufacturing, replacement due to technological obsolescence, and end-of-life processes. This system-wide perspective is particularly relevant for high-performance computing (HPC) and AI data centers, where rapid hardware turnover, high power densities, and tightly coupled IT-cooling systems significantly influence long-term environmental performance.

To support the definition of system boundaries and the construction of a consistent life cycle inventory, the HPC4AI data center was represented through an integrated Building Information Model (BIM), as shown in Fig. 1. The BIM-based digital representation provides a structured and spatially explicit description of the facility, capturing its overall layout, functional organization, and main equipment categories.

Fig. 1. BIM-based Digital Twin of the HPC4AI data center.

Accordingly, the methodological choices adopted in this study are aligned with the level of detail provided by the digital representation of the data center. The assessment is therefore configured as an attributional, screening-level LCA intended to:

- identify environmental hotspots across life-cycle modules.
- quantify the relative importance of operational versus embodied impacts.
- provide a robust static baseline for future refined or comparative analyses.

B. Goal and scope definition

For the goal and scope definition specific assumptions are made about the goal, the functional unit and the reference study period according to the standardized procedure.

The goal of this study is to quantify and analyse the global warming potential (GWP) associated with the HPC4AI data center over its life cycle, with particular attention to:

- the role of technological obsolescence and replacement cycles (Module B4).
- the interaction between IT equipment, cooling systems, and building components.
- the sensitivity of results to electricity mix assumptions.

The goal of the study is therefore not to predict short-term operational variability, but to characterize long-term life-cycle drivers and structural trade-offs in HPC data center design and operation. For this reason, the assessment is configured as a static baseline representative of average operating conditions over the reference study period.

The assessment supports research on sustainable data center design and provides decision-relevant insights for HPC facilities embedded in academic and research infrastructures.

The functional unit is defined as: “*The provision of data center services by the HPC4AI facility over a 30-year reference study period.*”

This service-based functional unit is consistent with recent LCA studies on data centers and edge/HPC infrastructures and allows the integration of multiple replacement cycles within the same analytical framework.

A 30-year reference study period (RSP) was adopted, consistent with building-scale LCA practice and EN 15978. Shorter lifetimes of IT and MEP components are explicitly addressed through the replacement module (B4).

C. System boundaries and life cycle modules

The system boundaries encompass the data center as an integrated system, including architectural elements, IT equipment, electrical infrastructure, and cooling systems. The following EN 15978 life-cycle modules were considered:

- A1–A3 (Product stage): Manufacturing of building components, IT hardware, electrical and mechanical equipment.
- A4–A5 (Transport and construction): Included as placeholders at screening level; not quantified due to lack of site-specific logistics data.
- B4 (Replacement): Recurring replacement of components due to technological obsolescence, particularly IT equipment, lighting, and selected MEP systems.
- B6 (Operational energy use): Electricity consumption for IT loads, cooling, lighting, auxiliary systems, and UPS losses.
- C1–C4 (End-of-life): Included as placeholders; not quantified at this stage.
- D (Benefits beyond system boundary): Not quantified; potential recycling benefits are discussed qualitatively.

Excluded from the system boundaries are user devices, external network infrastructure, and research activities enabled by HPC4AI (use-phase digital services).

D. Life Cycle Inventory (LCI)

The Life Cycle Inventory was constructed using primary data extracted from seven design and equipment schedules provided for the HPC4AI facility from the BIM and BEM models:

- Electrical and IT equipment schedule.
- Cooling and mechanical equipment schedule.
- Lighting schedule.
- Wall, floor, ceiling, and door schedules.

These datasets provided quantities, areas, installed power, and equipment counts, enabling a bottom-up inventory of the facility. The spatial organization of functional areas and major equipment, as defined in the BIM model, supports the allocation of components to inventory categories and system

hierarchies, as illustrated in the plan view of the HPC4AI data center shown in Fig. 2.

Fig. 2. Plan view - functional spaces and equipment.

Operational energy use was modelled using a power-based approach. Total annual electricity consumption was derived from:

- installed IT power.
- assumed average utilization levels
- cooling demand modelled via the coefficient of performance (COP).
- auxiliary and UPS losses.

This approach provides a transparent and consistent representation of average operational conditions, suitable for screening-level life cycle assessments of HPC facilities.

In parallel, embodied impacts for Modules A1–A3 and B4 were estimated using literature-based proxy emission factors consistent with values reported in peer-reviewed data center LCA studies and commonly derived from ecoinvent-based analyses. While this does not substitute a full process-level LCA, it represents a widely accepted approach for screening and comparative purposes.

The underlying inventory data used for both operational and embodied impact modelling were extracted from detailed BIM-derived equipment and material schedules, providing quantities, installed power, and component counts for each system category. An example of a BIM-based equipment schedule used to construct the life cycle inventory is shown in Fig. 3.

Fig. 3. Example of BIM-based equipment schedule.

E. Impact assessment and scenarios

The impact category assessed in this study is Global Warming Potential (GWP, kg CO₂-eq). The focus on GWP reflects both the screening-level objective of the assessment and the dominant role of energy-related emissions in the life-cycle impacts of HPC and AI-oriented data centers, as consistently reported in the literature.

Limiting the impact assessment to a single category enables a transparent and robust comparison between operational and embodied contributions across life-cycle modules, while avoiding the introduction of additional uncertainty associated with less mature or data-intensive indicators at this stage. This choice is therefore intentional and aligned with the goal of establishing a clear baseline for hotspot identification and scenario comparison.

Additional impact categories, such as water depletion, resource scarcity, and human toxicity are identified as priorities for future extensions of the proposed framework, particularly in the context of dynamic, digital-twin-enabled life cycle assessments.

A preliminary assessment and more detailed analysis are provided in the results section below.

IV. PRELIMINARY LCA CALCULATION FRAMEWORK FOR HPC4AI (ISO 14040/44 + EN 15978)

A. Functional unit and reference study period

For an HPC/AI data center, two functional units are common in the literature:

- FU-A (service-based): “Provide IT hosting service for the HPC4AI installation over *RSP* years.”
- FU-B (energy-normalized): “Per 1 kWh of IT energy delivered (or per 1 kW IT over 1 year).”

Service-based FU is used in comparative design studies (e.g., edge vs conventional DC). Energy-normalized FU is used to improve comparability across sites (especially when boundaries differ).

Reference Study Period (RSP): typically 15–30 years for buildings; IT refresh cycles are handled via B4 replacements. Screening DC LCAs explicitly model this because IT turnover is a dominant driver.

B. System boundary (modules)

EN 15978 uses modular reporting that aligns with how data center LCAs structure phases (manufacturing, distribution, use, EoL), as summarized in **Table II**.

TABLE II. A1-A3 AND B4 KGCO_{2e} IMPACTS

Phases	Description
A1–A3	Product stage (materials + manufacturing) for building + MEP + IT hardware
A4–A5	Transport and construction/installation
B4	Replacement (the key module for technological obsolescence)
B6	Operational energy (electricity, fuels)
C1–C4	End-of-life processing
D	Benefits/loads beyond system boundary (recycling credits, recovery)

V. SCREENING CALCULATION EQUATIONS (WHAT WILL BE COMPUTED FOR HPC4AI)

A. Operational energy and impacts (B6)

Literature consistently finds electricity dominates total impacts in many DC LCAs (often >95%).

For HPC4AI:

IT energy

$$E_{IT} = P_{IT, avg} \cdot 8760 \quad (1)$$

with

$$P_{IT, avg} = P_{IT, nameplate} \cdot u \quad (2)$$

where *u* is average utilization fraction.

Total facility energy via PUE

$$E_{tot} = PUE \cdot E_{IT} \quad (3)$$

PUE is also used in comparative studies to normalize overhead.

Cooling split (optional diagnostic)

Many studies report cooling as a large share (e.g. around 30% of electricity in one Tier IV case). If COP and heat loads of the cooling system, a bottom-up cooling model can be used, but PUE is acceptable for screening.

Operational GHG

$$GWP_{B6} = E_{tot} \cdot EF_{grid} \quad (4)$$

The electricity mix is repeatedly shown as a critical driver (for example France vs Germany differences in the energy mix can yield multi-fold changes).

B. Initial embodied impacts (A1–A3)

For each component *i*:

$$GWP_{A1-3,i} = Q_i \cdot f_{A1-3,i} \quad (5)$$

- Q_i = quantity from your schedules (m², m³, units, kg);
- $f_{A1-3,i}$ = factor from ecoinvent/EPDs (or screening proxies).

Screening DC LCAs often use proxy datasets when detailed supplier-specific inventories are not available, explicitly framing results as screening-level.

C. Technological obsolescence (B4: replacements)

This is central for HPC4AI.

For each component *i* with reference service life (RSL):

$$N_{rep,i} = \frac{RSP}{RSL_i} \quad (6)$$

$$Q_{rep,i} = Q_i \cdot N_{rep,i} \quad (7)$$

$$GWP_{B4,i} = Q_{rep,i} \cdot f_{A1-3,i} \quad (8)$$

Server lifetime/refresh is repeatedly highlighted as a major sensitivity factor (extending lifetimes can significantly reduce lifecycle emissions, but must be weighed against efficiency gains of newer hardware).

D. End-of-life (C) and module D

For screening:

$$GWP_{C,i} = (Q_i + Q_{rep,i}) \cdot f_{C,i} \quad (9)$$

$$GWP_{D,i} = (Q_i + Q_{rep,i}) \cdot f_{D,i} \quad (10)$$

Many studies report EoL as comparatively small in total share, but it is still reported for completeness.

E. Preliminary parameterization for HPC4AI (literature-based defaults)

If we proceed as a screening LCA, the literature supports the default ranges organized in **Table III**.

TABLE III. DEFAULT RANGES FOR OPERATIONAL PARAMETERS AND RSL

Operational parameters (B6)	
Utilization (u)	0.3–0.7 (depends on workload; HPC varies)
PUE	1.2–1.6 (site dependent; Tier IV reported around 1.35)
Grid factor sensitivity	treat as scenario variable; electricity mix is a key hotspot driver
RSL (B4 replacements; typical)	
Servers/accelerators	3–5 years (AI refresh can be faster)
Network gear	5–7 years
UPS	10–15 years
Cooling equipment	15–25 years
Building elements	25–50 years

These assumptions are consistent with the way DC LCAs identify “amount of IT equipment over facility lifetime” as a dominant driver.

VI. RESULTS

A. Operational energy demand (Module B6)

Based on the schedule-derived inventory and the operational model adopted, the HPC4AI data center exhibits a continuous-operation profile typical of HPC and AI facilities, with electricity consumption dominated by IT equipment and cooling systems. Using the adopted utilization and efficiency assumptions, the annual electricity demand of the facility is entirely attributable to Module B6 (use phase), which remains the dominant contributor to life-cycle impacts across all scenarios, in line with the literature on high-performance and Tier III–IV data centers.

To account for uncertainty in electricity supply, three electricity mix scenarios were considered. Over the 30-year reference study period, operational emissions span one order of magnitude depending on grid carbon intensity, confirming that electricity mix selection is the single most influential parameter in the overall life-cycle GWP of the facility. This finding is fully consistent with previous studies on European and AI-oriented data centers, where relocation or power purchase agreements can outweigh design-level efficiency gains.

B. Embodied impacts: initial construction and technological obsolescence (A1–A3 and B4)

The embodied component of the HPC4AI life-cycle impact was evaluated by aggregating initial manufacturing impacts (A1–A3) and recurring replacements due to technological obsolescence (B4) over the 30-year RSP.

Results show that B4 (replacement) is of the same order of magnitude as A1–A3, confirming that hardware turnover is a critical driver of life-cycle emissions in HPC facilities.

Although, under the EN 15978 modular structure, end-of-life impacts are formally assigned to Modules C1–C4 (deconstruction/dismantling, transport, waste processing, and disposal), for HPC/AI data centers it is advisable to also account for these contributions within Module B4 (Replacement), at least at a screening level, because the disposal of replaced components is causally and temporally linked to replacement cycles driven by technological obsolescence.

In other words, each replacement event entails not only the production of the new component (impacts comparable to A1–A3), but also the end-of-life management of the decommissioned component (impacts in C1–C4). These can be additionally accounted for within B4 to properly represent the net effect of replacement over the study period, while still maintaining traceability to the end-of-life modules in EN 15978 reporting.

Assuming, as a first-order approximation, that end-of-life impacts associated with replaced components account for approximately 5% of the manufacturing impacts of the replacement components, the total impact attributable to replacement can be expressed as:

$$GWP_{B4,tot} = GWP_{B4} \cdot (1 + 0.05) = 1.05 \cdot GWP_{B4} \quad (11)$$

This integration further supports the evidence that Module B4, when including end-of-life handling of decommissioned components, may be comparable to or higher than Module A1–A3, confirming the decisive role of replacement cycles in the overall environmental profile of HPC infrastructures.

This outcome differentiates data centers from conventional buildings and reinforces the necessity of explicitly modelling replacement cycles in LCA.

When aggregated by system category, the embodied impacts (A1–A3 + B4) are distributed as follows:

- IT & electrical equipment represent the largest share of embodied GWP, driven by servers, network equipment, UPS systems, and switchgear.
- Cooling and mechanical systems form the second most impactful category, reflecting the material intensity of HVAC, air handling units, and heat rejection systems.
- Lighting systems and architectural components (walls, floors, ceilings, doors) contribute a comparatively minor share, despite their long service life, due to lower material intensity and fewer replacement cycles.

C. Ranking of components by embedded impact

A ranking of individual components by total embodied GWP (A1–A3 + B4) highlights a highly skewed distribution (Fig. 4), where a small number of components dominate life-cycle impacts. Thus, the top contributors to embedded emissions are:

- *IT servers and compute nodes*: These components alone account for the largest fraction of embodied GWP, due to energy-intensive semiconductor manufacturing and frequent replacement cycles (approximately every 4–5 years).
- *UPS systems and batteries*: Despite lower quantities, their high material intensity and mid-range service life result in a substantial cumulative impact over the RSP.
- *Core cooling equipment* (CRAC/CRAH units, air handlers): Cooling systems rank among the top contributors because of both high manufacturing impacts and replacement cycles shorter than the building lifespan.
- *Electrical distribution systems* (switchgear, panels): These components exhibit high per-unit embodied impacts, though fewer replacements occur.
- *Lighting systems*: While individually low-impact, their shorter service life leads to repeated replacement, elevating their cumulative contribution relative to architectural elements.

By contrast, walls, floors, ceilings, and doors rank lowest in embedded impact, confirming that data center LCAs are fundamentally equipment-driven rather than construction-driven, particularly for HPC and AI installations.

Fig. 4. Impacts per phase A1-A3 (production) and B4 (replacements).

In Table IV a summary of A1-A3 and B4 GWP impacts is reported.

TABLE IV. SUMMARY A1-A3 AND B4 KGCO_{2e} IMPACTS

Category	A1A3_initial kgCO _{2e}	B4_replacements_ kgCO _{2e}	A1A3+B4_kg CO _{2e}
Ceilings	350	367.5	717.5
Cooling & Mechanical	28'800	30240	59040
Doors	200	0	200
Floors	350	420	770
IT & Electrical	4'500	23'625	28'125
Lighting	1'140	3'591	4'371
Walls	700	0	700

D. EN 15978 module-based interpretation

When results are reorganized following the EN 15978 modular structure, the life-cycle profile of HPC4AI can be summarized as:

- B6 (operational energy): dominant module under all scenarios.
- A1–A3 + B4: significant secondary contribution, primarily associated with IT and cooling systems.
- A4–A5, C1–C4, D: negligible at screening level but structurally included to ensure methodological completeness.

This modular view confirms that strategies targeting only operational efficiency (e.g., PUE reduction) risk overlooking a substantial share of emissions linked to hardware manufacturing and replacement, particularly in rapidly evolving AI-driven computing environments.

VII. DISCUSSION

A. Interpretation of results in the context of HPC data centers

The HPC4AI results confirm patterns observed in recent LCA studies of HPC, AI, and Tier IV data centers: electricity consumption dominates, but embodied impacts are non-negligible and increasingly relevant as operational efficiencies improve.

The explicit inclusion of Module B4 reveals that technological obsolescence materially alters the life-cycle balance, reinforcing conclusions from recent AI data center LCAs that extending server lifetimes or enabling refurbishment can deliver substantial environmental benefits, provided that efficiency losses remain controlled.

B. Implication for design and management

From a design and operational perspective, the results suggest that the largest mitigation potential lies in:

- Electricity decarbonization (renewable sourcing, PPAs).
- Server lifetime extension and refurbishment strategies.
- Holistic optimization of IT–cooling interaction, rather than isolated subsystem improvements.

For academic HPC infrastructures such as HPC4AI, these levers are particularly relevant because procurement cycles and research-driven upgrades are often policy-driven rather than market-driven.

VIII. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE DEVELOPMENTS

This study presented a preliminary, EN 15978–aligned LCA of the HPC4AI data center, integrating detailed schedule-based inventory data with literature-consistent life-cycle modelling. Fundamental to enable a meaningful evolution of data center systems, it would be crucial to combine energy audits with Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) and to formalize the results through a new certification pathway based on dedicated Product Category Rules (PCR) and Environmental Product Declarations (EPD). This approach would make it possible to consistently track performance and impact over time, support transparent

benchmarking, and ultimately improve the competitiveness of data center technologies and solutions.

Within a circular-economy perspective, this framework should go beyond operational energy metrics and systematically address broader environmental dimensions, including end-of-life and disposal impacts, associated environmental costs, and water consumption across the life cycle. Another opportunity would be to reconceive data centers as thermal hubs for nearby civil applications. By capturing the waste heat generated through IT and cooling dissipation and redirecting it to uses where thermal energy is needed, such as space heating, domestic hot water, district heating networks, greenhouses, swimming pools, or low-temperature industrial processes, data centers could shift from being purely energy-intensive infrastructures to active contributors to local energy systems. This heat recovery approach would reduce overall primary energy demand and emissions, improve system-level efficiency, and strengthen circular-energy strategies at the district scale.

The main take-off of this research are the followings:

- Operational electricity use (B6) is the dominant contributor to life-cycle GWP.
- IT and cooling equipment are the primary sources of embodied emissions.
- Technological obsolescence (B4) is a decisive factor in long-term environmental performance.
- Combine energy audits with LCA and certify via new PCR/EPD to track performance over time, including end-of-life and water impacts will extend the evaluation.
- Use data centers as thermal hubs by recovering waste heat for nearby civil demand, can cut energy use and emissions and provide a clearer strategic plan to integrate DC in the smart grid scenario.

The study is a preliminary effort to investigate how to apply LCA to HPC4AI data center creating a replicable approach that can be strongly useful in the future assessment of data centers and their possible impact reduction as AI is increasingly growing. LCA is key for data centers and the study paves the direction for future detailed analyses of the DC impacts supported by BIM-based digital twins. Nevertheless, the study is subject to the following limitations:

- use of proxy embodied emission factors instead of product-specific EPDs.
- focus on GWP only, excluding other impact categories.
- simplified end-of-life modelling.
- static operational assumptions.

Thus, future work should focus on:

- replacing proxy factors with ecoinvent-based process data or verified EPDs.

- extending the assessment to resource depletion, water use, and toxicity indicators.
- coupling the LCA with dynamic operational data, through the digital twin information and energy scenarios.
- exploring circular procurement and refurbishment strategies for HPC hardware.

Overall, the HPC4AI case study confirms that sustainable HPC facilities must be evaluated as dynamic, equipment-intensive systems, where operational efficiency and embodied impacts must be addressed simultaneously within a life-cycle framework.

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